

GLOBAL TRADE PERFORMANCE OF DATE'S (*Phoenix dactylifera Lnn.*) A FOREIGN TRADE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The study examines the international trade performance of dates and the study was conducted by collecting secondary data on exports-imports of dates from 52 countries distributed across six continents. This study analyses the growth rates of international trading prices, Instability index, EUV, IUV, Terms of Trade (TOT), trade price elasticities and trends of date. The study concluded that the annual growth of exports and imports of dates was around 4.80 percent and 4.78 percent in the world, respectively. The study noticed that more than 85% of the dates were exported by only six countries viz., UAE, Iraq, Iran, Pakistan, Tunisia and Saudi Arabia in the world. Whereas, more than 60% of dates were imported by India, UAE, Morocco, France and Yemen during study period. The study concluded that UAE is leader in exports of dates with around 24 percent of the total volume traded, but it represented only 10.08 percent of the market in terms of value. Although, India's is considered as major importers (36% in volume traded) of dates in the world but it represented only 16 percent of the market in terms of (US\$) values. The export price elasticity for Tunisia, Egypt, Germany, Netherlands, Iraq, Jordan, USA, Pakistan and Saudi Arabia was elastic in nature, whereas for UAE, Iran, France and Oman were inelastic. The export price elastic countries may gain extra foreign exchange revenue if they reduce their exports prices of dates. The USA, Israel, Netherlands, Germany, France, Jordan, Saudi Arabia, Egypt, Pakistan and Niger have comparative advantage in exports of dates and enjoy's better TOT whereas UAE, Tunisia and Iran have comparative disadvantage in exports might be due to more import price than export. The study concluded that UAE was emerged as leader in exports of dates with around 24 percent of the total volume traded, but it represented only 10.08 percent of the market share in terms of value during study period. Although, India's is considered as major importers (36% in volume traded) of dates in the world but it represented only 16 percent of the market in terms of (US\$) values during study period. The study showed that terms of trade (TOT) of all importing countries improved including India except UAE and Malaysia. It revealed that the largest exporters such as UAE and Iran market share is less in terms of values; both showed a deterioration TOT may be due to more imports price than exports.

Keywords: World prices, TOT, Trade price elasticity, EUV, IUV, emerging medicinal food,

Introduction

Date palms fruit are considered as ancient nutritional power house and emerging future medicinal food (Praveen, 2012). It is highly nutritious and offers an unbeatable combination of versatile utility with nutrition and numerous health benefits (Andres, 2016). It has many nutritional and health promoting components and the consumption of 100g of dates can provide over 15% of the RDA minerals. Vitamins B-complex and C are the major vitamins in dates (Mohamed Ali Al-Farsi and Chang Yong Lee, 2008). The cultivation of date fruits is fairly widespread in the Arabic countries, Africa and Israel (Shah, 2014) and is marketed all over the world as a high value confectionery fruit crop.

World price means a price for a good or services in all countries other than one's own (Financial Dictionary, 2012). The world market economy depends on world price signals to correctly allocate its scarce resources and stabilize domestic market (David Hallam, 2003). World price of dates influences on international trade. Under modern capitalism, major commercial exports and imports of a country conducted in world prices (Encyclopedia, 2010). A country exports goods and services with local price lower than the world price. On other hand, it imports goods and services with higher local prices than the world price (Financial Dictionary, 2012). Based on above explanations the exports and imports prices are considered as world trading prices (Dastagir and Jainuddin, 2017).

Economic precision is required on international prices, imports and exports (Dastagir and Jainuddin, 2017). There are no or limited empirical studies on Dates trading prices signals. This study analyses trade signals of exports, imports and prices of major dates trading countries in the world. Finally, the study will helps to suggest strategies for promotion of trade in the Date palm. The specific objectives of the study are;

1. To analyze the world trading prices of Date palm
2. To estimate export and import price growth rates, trends and instability of Date palm
3. To analyze the terms of trade, export and import price elasticities of Date palm
4. To suggest strategies and foreign trade policy to boost Date palm trade

Material And Methods

This is basically a foreign trade research study covers 52 major dates exporting and importing countries in the world. The study period is 2000-01 to 2015-16. These 52 countries are distributed across the continents viz., Asia (27 countries), Europe (14 countries), Africa (6 countries), North America (3 countries) and Australia (2 countries). Out of 52 countries, top 15 countries were chosen based on major share of exports (97%) and imports (82%) of dates in the world and rest as other countries. The required secondary data of dates were collected from published sources like APEDA, DGCIS, NHB, FAOSTAT, CMIE Commodities, EXIM, Foreign Trade Year Book, RBI, Planning commission reports etc.

This research used the simple tabular analysis, CAGR (Damodar and Sangeetha, 2007), Instability Index, Terms of Trade as ratio of export price to import price (Dastagir and Jainuddin, 2017) for analysis in the study. The export import price elasticity were estimated by using midpoint elasticity method (Dastagir and Jainuddin, 2017; Subba Reddy *et al.*, 2019). Three year moving average method was employed to find out the exports imports trends of dates.

Export Unit Value (EUV) and Import Unit Value (IUV)

EUV is the commodity's export price was determined as ratio of export value to export quantity of the dates. IUV is the commodity's imports price was estimated by the ratio of imports value to imports quantity of dates (Adeeth Cariappa and Chandel, 2020).

Export Import Price elasticity formulae: The export import price elasticity of Dates were estimated by using midpoint elasticity method (Dastgiri and Jainuddin, 2017; Subba reddy *et al.*, 2019).

$SPe = \% \text{ change in quantity exports} / \% \text{ change in price}$

The percentage change in quantity exports imports is $\% \Delta Q$, and the percentage change in price is $\% \Delta P$. We calculate $\% \Delta Q$ as $\Delta Q/Q_{ave}$ and We Calculate $\% \Delta P$ as $\Delta P/P_{ave}$. So, we calculate the price elasticity of exports imports as $(\Delta Q/Q_{ave})/(\Delta P/P_{ave})$

Instability Index Formulae: Coefficient of variation = (Standard Deviation / Mean) *100

Terms of Trade calculation: It is measured by the ratio of export price to import price (Dastgiri and Jainuddin, 2017).

$$TOTAL = \frac{\text{Average Price of Exports}}{\text{Average Price of Imports}} = P_x/P_m$$

↑ Price M or ↓ Price X → Deterioration ToT

↓ Price M or ↑ Price X → Improvement ToT

Results And Discussion

Exports and Imports of Dates in world

The dates exporting countries and their share in the world exports were presented in the Table 1. Around 52 countries are involved in trading of dates in the world. Among the 52 countries, top 15 countries are accounted major share in exports (97%) and imports (82%) of dates in the world. Out of 15 exporting countries only seven countries (Table 1) exported more than 90 percent of dates during study period. Although, UAE exports accounted around 24 percent of the total volume traded, but it represented only 10.08 percent of the share in market in terms of value. Tunisia, Iran and Israel contributed around 46 percent to world trade of dates in terms of value while they together accounts only 28 percent of the total volume traded in exports. Among the dates exporting countries, Tunisia has earned the highest foreign exchange revenue followed by Iran, Israel, UAE, Saudi Arabia and Pakistan. It might be due to Tunisia largely exported to European Countries. The study in line with Liu, (2002) confirmed the Tunisia largely benefited from rise in imported quantities by European Union countries. The study showed that the USA has received the highest average export prices followed by Israel, Netherland, Germany and France. The export price of Tunisia was more or less stable and higher than compared to other exporters. It might be due to their strategy of targeting the high value European markets (Botes and Zaid, 2002; Liu, 2002).

The dates importing countries and their share in the world imports were presented in the Table 2. Although, India's imports around 36 percent of the total volume traded, but it represents only 16 percent of the market share in terms of US dollars. The highest imports prices were fetched by UK and France countries may be due to that these countries import more expensive and higher quality dates. The EU is an important market for exporting countries, as it primarily imports dates of high value (Liu, 2002). The imports price of France was more or less stable and more than compared to other importers may be due to imports more expensive and higher quality dates (Botes and Zaid, 2002). France imports mainly from Tunisia and Algeria significant quantities of natural dates in bulk which are then processed, packed and re-exported (Liu, 2002)

Growth rates and Instability Index of Date

The CAGR and instability index of dates exports and imports were presented in Table 3 and 4, respectively. The study showed that during 2000-01 to 2015-16, the exports of dates were increased from 5.32 lakh tonnes to 11.29 lakh tonnes with 4.81 percent annual growth rate in the world. The steady increase in the export of dates was noticed in Israel and Egypt, Netherlands, Jordan, Germany, Tunisia and Iraq, UAE, Iran, and France. The study showed that the annual growth rate of exports price of dates was higher for Jordan followed by Iran, Saudi Arabia, UAE, USA and Oman. It might be due to the exports to more expensive markets (Liu, 2002).

The study found that the imports of dates (Table 4) increased from 4.99 lakh tonnes to 10.53 lakh tonnes with 4.78 percent annual growth in the world during study period. All dates importing countries showed stability in imports of dates except UAE. The annual growth in imports price was found to be higher for Turkey followed by Russia, Pakistan, Indonesia, UAE and India. It might be due to higher value for the imported dates (Liu, 2002).

Exports and Imports Price elasticity's of Date

Export-imports price elasticity's of top 15 countries were represented in Table 5. The study showed that the export price elasticity for exporting countries such as UAE, Iran, France, Oman and Niger was inelastic in nature. It may indicated that percentage change in quantity exported (21.62% for UAE) is smaller than the percentage change in export price (72.98% for UAE) of dates during study period. It indicates exports or imports responsiveness to changes in price (Dastagiri and Jainuddin, 2017). The imports price elasticity was inelastic in nature for importing countries such as India, Russia,

Indonesia, Malaysia and Turkey. It indicates that percentage change in imports of dates (58.01% for India) is smaller than the percentage change in imports price (94.63% for India) of dates during study period. The study showed that exports-imports price elasticity for dates was inelastic in nature for both exporting importing countries. These export price inelastic countries interest to reduce the quantity of the good reaching to the world markets (Scobie and Johnson, 1979).

Terms of Trade (TOT) of Dates

The average export import prices and TOT of dates exporting and importing countries were presented in Table 6. The study showed that all importing as well as exporting countries have comparative advantages in exports-imports of dates. TOT of all exporting countries improved except the largest date's exporting countries such as UAE, Tunisia and Iran as they have comparative disadvantage in exports. All importing countries have comparative advantages in date's imports except UAE and Malaysia as these two countries terms of trade worsened may be due imports price are more than exports price (Dastagiri and Jainuddin, 2017).

Export import trends of Dates

Three year moving average method was employed to find out the export imports trends of dates. The exports quantity and export price trends of dates were presented in Figure 1 and 2. The export quantity of dates for Iran, Pakistan, Tunisia and Saudi Arabia are more or less witnessed a stable trend during the study period. Similar trend was noticed for exports price of UAE, Iraq, Pakistan, Tunisia and Saudi Arabia during study period. The imports price and quantity of dates in India, France and Yemen was stable except Morocco for quantity

Conclusions

Date palm fruit provides an unbeatable combination of versatile utility with numerous health benefits and is emerging as future medicinal food. World trading price signal influences on international trade. There are no or limited empirical studies are there on dates trading prices signals. This foreign trade research study examines the export and import of dates of total 52 countries distributed across six continents from 2000-01 to 2015-16. The UAE and India are emerged as world's largest exporter and importer of dates during study period, respectively. The more than 85 percent of the dates were exported by top six net exporters and more than 60 percent of dates imported by top five net importers in the world. The export price elasticity for exporting countries such as Tunisia, Egypt, Germany, Netherlands, Iraq, Jordan, USA, Pakistan and Saudi Arabia was elastic in nature. The export price elastic countries may gain extra foreign exchange revenue if they reduce their exports prices of dates.

The study concluded that the percentage share of UAE and Iran in market is less in terms of values; both have deterioration TOT may be due to more imports price and less exports prices. UAE, Iran, France and Oman has price inelastic in nature.

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Table 1: Top 15 Export Destinations of Dates in the world (2000-01 to 2015-16)

Countries	Total Quantity (tonnes)	% of Qty to World total	Total Value (1000 US\$)	% of value to World total	Average price (US\$/Kg)	% Share Average Price
UAE	3006147	23.96	1100063	10.08	0.42	1.44
Iraq	2016645	16.08	541178	4.96	0.26	0.90
Iran	1925792	15.35	1282394	11.75	0.67	2.30
Pakistan	1825046	14.55	849548	7.79	0.44	1.50
Tunisia	1179472	9.40	2591555	23.75	2.14	7.27
Saudi Arabia	1071608	8.54	1039785	9.53	0.90	3.06
Israel	421580	3.36	1165830	10.69	4.21	14.35
Egypt	225059	1.79	238621	2.19	0.89	3.05
France	171442	1.37	455642	4.18	2.64	9.01
Oman	137668	1.10	107837	0.99	0.76	2.60
UAS	84459	0.67	459276	4.21	5.13	17.45
Niger	46014	0.37	9749	0.09	0.24	0.81
Jordan	45014	0.36	73783	0.68	1.41	4.79
Netherlands	44477	0.35	177328	1.63	3.84	13.09
Germany	42077	0.34	146421	1.34	3.34	11.37
Other Countries	302685	2.41	671891	6.16	2.06	7.02
World Total	12545185	100.00	10910901	100.00	29.37	100.00

Data Sources: FAOSTAT, 2019 Accessed on 7th August, 2019**Table 2: Top 15 Import Destinations of Dates in the world (2000-01 to 2015-16)**

Countries	Total Quantity (tonnes)	% of Qty to World total	Total Value (1000 US\$)	% of value to World total	Average price (US\$/Kg)	% Share Average Price
India	4369889	35.08	1716680	16.11	0.37	2.36
United Arab Emirates	1613115	12.95	628271	5.90	0.64	4.10
Morocco	705606	5.66	908398	8.53	1.20	7.64
France	453487	3.64	1030048	9.67	2.26	14.38
Yemen	419573	3.37	201954	1.90	0.46	2.96
Russian Federation	318331	2.56	276611	2.60	0.85	5.44
Pakistan	310836	2.49	77755	0.73	0.38	2.45
Bangladesh	296102	2.38	127315	1.19	0.52	3.34
Indonesia	287457	2.31	272142	2.55	0.81	5.17
Malaysia	271365	2.18	466476	4.38	1.61	10.27

USA	255374	2.05	352848	3.31	1.35	8.58
United Kingdom	244873	1.97	565116	5.30	2.26	14.42
Turkey	239662	1.92	174745	1.64	0.62	3.98
Niger	228391	1.83	24509	0.23	0.11	0.68
China	219292	1.76	137761	1.29	0.64	4.10
Other Countries	2225211	17.86	3693670	34.67	1.59	10.15
World total	12458564	100.00	10654299	100.00	15.68	100.00

Data Sources: FAOSTAT, 2019 Accessed on 7th August, 2019

Table 3: Growth rates and instability of top 15 exporting countries (2000-01 to 2015-16)

Export Countries	2000		2016		Growth Rate (%)		CV (%)	
	Export Quantity	Export price						
UAE	222030	0.27	275863	0.58	1.37	4.90	60.71	50.35
Iraq	30000	0.20	150000	0.33	10.58	3.24	72.41	27.39
Iran	107847	0.24	138844	0.70	1.59	6.95	18.55	50.22
Pakistan	78661	0.38	163177	0.63	4.67	3.24	31.58	26.70
Tunisia	22411	1.72	113794	1.99	10.69	0.91	40.71	13.84
Saudi Arabia	28248	0.65	75441	1.43	6.33	5.06	48.58	26.22
Israel	1329	4.56	86890	1.63	29.86	-6.23	131.24	32.33
Egypt	2669	0.66	34561	0.82	17.36	1.32	88.53	57.61
France	9576	1.96	13029	2.89	1.94	2.46	17.02	14.90
Oman	9881	0.47	15700	0.81	2.94	3.48	44.52	46.65
USA	3183	3.61	8502	6.90	6.33	4.13	37.57	28.49
Niger	3162	0.28	2348	0.18	-1.84	-2.60	69.72	27.08
Jordan	633	0.70	5612	2.31	14.61	7.71	48.44	43.89
Netherlands	533	2.76	5908	4.21	16.22	2.68	67.56	14.56
Germany	699	2.41	5878	3.57	14.23	2.47	56.63	13.50
Other Countries	11776	1.16	33765	2.52	6.81	4.96	43.97	28.96
World Total	532638	0.45	1129312	0.87	4.81	5.35	32.38	33.84

Data Sources: FAOSTAT, 2019 Accessed on 7th August, 2019

Table 4: Growth rates and instability of top 15 importing countries (2000-01 to 2015-16)

Countries	2000-01		2016-17		Growth Rate (%)		CV (%)	
	Import Quantity	Import Price						
India	192619	0.22	350022	0.60	3.80	6.64	20.57	45.94
UAE	44000	0.18	213821	0.56	10.39	7.32	101.01	86.09
Morocco	5434	1.12	69324	1.39	17.25	1.33	43.84	44.94
France	23530	1.71	33910	2.24	2.31	1.72	13.80	15.21
Yemen	12587	0.48	33578	0.43	6.76	1.91	32.00	17.50
Russian	8834	0.18	17312	1.28	4.29	13.10	22.05	59.93
Pakistan	29547	0.18	5599	1.21	-9.87	12.76	82.15	71.45
Bangladesh	17500	0.46	37340	0.60	4.85	1.65	70.79	49.60
Indonesia	13316	0.25	23229	1.42	3.54	11.40	38.98	53.40
Malaysia	11158	0.88	18271	2.31	3.13	6.24	18.76	40.86
USA	4667	1.02	28573	1.74	11.99	3.24	86.13	15.82
UK	10430	1.59	19807	2.81	4.09	3.62	19.64	18.69
Turkey	8514	0.13	26772	1.36	7.42	15.69	42.99	57.52
Niger	8602	0.09	13089	0.14	2.66	2.57	32.14	15.44
China	12823	0.82	8001	0.63	-2.90	-1.65	35.88	19.02
Other Countries	95526	1.04	187584	2.03	4.31	4.27	28.18	21.29
World Total	499087	0.53	1053418	1.10	4.78	4.70	26.25	33.51

Data Sources: FAOSTAT, 2019 Accessed on 7th August, 2019

Table 5: Trade Price elasticity's of dates in the world (2000-01 to 2015-16)

Exporting Countries	Top 15 Dates Exporting Countries			Importing Countries	Top 15 Dates Importing Countries		
	% Δ in Export Quantity	% Δ in Export Price	Export Price Elasticity		% Δ in Import Quantity	% Δ in Import Price	Imports Price Elasticity
UAE	21.62	72.98	0.30	India	58.01	94.63	0.61
Iraq	133.33	50.00	2.67	UAE	131.74	102.33	1.29

Iran	25.13	98.24	0.26	Morocco	143.05	41.88	3.42
Pakistan	69.89	49.96	1.40	France	36.17	27.05	1.34
Tunisia	134.18	14.52	9.24	Yemen	90.94	28.12	3.23
Saudi Arabia	91.03	75.11	1.21	Russian	64.85	151.05	0.43
Israel	193.97	-94.65	-2.05	Pakistan	-136.28	148.93	-0.92
Egypt	171.32	20.94	8.18	Bangladesh	72.36	25.96	2.79
France	30.55	38.37	0.80	Indonesia	54.25	139.62	0.39
Oman	45.49	53.44	0.85	Malaysia	48.34	89.91	0.54
USA	91.04	62.63	1.45	USA	143.84	52.54	2.74
Niger	-29.55	-41.55	0.71	UK	62.02	55.46	1.12
Jordan	159.46	106.59	1.50	Turkey	103.49	164.58	0.63
Netherlands	166.90	41.72	4.00	Niger	41.37	40.10	1.03
Germany	157.49	38.59	4.08	China	-46.31	-26.54	1.75
Other Countries	96.57	73.81	1.31	Other Countries	65.03	64.46	1.01
World	71.08	78.85	0.91	World	71.41	70.40	1.01

Data Sources: FAOSTAT, 2019 Accessed on 7th August, 2019

Table 6: Terms of Trade of Dates in the world (2000-01 to 2015-16)

Countries	Top 15 Exporting Countries			Countries	Top 15 Importing Countries		
	Average Export Price	Average Import Price	Terms of Trade		Average Export Price	Average Import Price	Terms of Trade
UAE	0.42	0.64	0.66	India	1.15	0.37	3.10
Iraq	0.26	-	-	UAE	0.42	0.64	0.66
Iran	0.67	1.02	0.66	Morocco	1.43	1.20	1.19
Pakistan	0.44	0.38	1.15	France	2.64	2.26	1.17
Tunisia	2.14	2.44	0.87	Yemen	0.68	0.46	1.47
Saudi Arabia	0.90	0.89	1.01	Russian	2.19	0.85	2.57
Israel	4.21	1.46	2.88	Pakistan	0.44	0.38	1.15
Egypt	0.89	0.75	1.19	Bangladesh	-	0.52	-
France	2.64	2.26	1.17	Indonesia	1.50	0.81	1.85
Oman	0.76	1.32	0.58	Malaysia	1.03	1.61	0.64
USA	5.13	1.35	3.81	USA	5.13	1.35	3.81
Niger	0.24	0.11	2.21	United Kingdom	2.67	2.26	1.18
Jordan	1.41	1.10	1.28	Turkey	1.18	0.62	1.90
Netherlands	3.84	2.98	1.29	Niger	0.24	0.11	2.21
Germany	3.34	2.50	1.33	China	1.94	0.64	3.02

Data Sources: FAOSTAT, 2019 Accessed on 7th August, 2019

Fig. 1 Export quantity trend of date's exporters

Fig. 2 Export price trend of date's exporters

Fig. 3 Imports quantity trend of date's importers

Fig. 4 Imports price trend of date's importers